

Thermoplastic Composites for Demanding Energy Environments: Some current studies

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From corrosion management to corrosion free: the non-metallic path

Courtesy: Novel

Courtesy: Composite worlds

Courtesy: Calcul Meca – HHR Roof.

Courtesy: CSUB

From corrosion management to corrosion free: the non-metallic path

Courtesy: Novel

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- No classical corrosion,
- Ideal for coastal, offshore, sour gas contexts,
- Reduced OPEX, lighter infrastructures,
- Huge potential for localizing the supply chain

Courtesy: CSUB

The non-metallic path: an enabler to sustainability

- Hydrogen value-chain:
 - No hydrogen embrittlement
- Carbon capture and storage context:
 - Wet CO₂
 - CO₂ mixed with impurities (Sox, Nox, etc..)

J. Sonke, W. Bos, and S. Paterson, "Materials challenges with CO₂ transport and injection for carbon capture and storage," *Int. J. Greenhouse Gas Control*, vol. 114, p. 103601, 2022

Two applications to be discussed

- Compressed hydrogen storage,
- Monitoring of high-performance thermoplastic pipes

Example 1

Thermoplastics thin-ply for compressed hydrogen storage

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Compressed mobile hydrogen storage: a need for the hydrogen value-chain

Toyota Mirai car with hydrogen tanks

Hydrogen power Jupiter H2 Drone

- Compressed Hydrogen tanks are essential for mobile applications,
- Typical conditions:
 - RT, [300-700] bars,
 - Multiple refueling cycle,
 - Safe to impact,
 - Maximum leak rate (app. 0.05g/h/Kg H₂)

Getting Compressed hydrogen storage lighter: type IV tank

- In all cases, most of the weight of a filled tank, is the tank,
- Composites enable larger tank-to-hydrogen weight ratio:
 - In Type III tanks: **[~22]**
 - In Type IV tanks: **[~12]**

H. Barthélémy, M. Weber, F. Barbier, Hydrogen storage: Recent improvements and industrial perspectives, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy 42 (11 (2017) 7254-7262.

Compressed mobile hydrogen storage: the challenges of type IV tank

Cavitation and blistering

Liner collapse

- Cavitation during depressurization in the liner or interface,
- Collapse of the liner due to
 - Liner/wall interface,
 - Lack of structural bearing capabilities of the liner

How to simultaneously

- Bring more structural stability?
- Save more weight ?

Getting Compressed hydrogen storage lighter : Moving to Type V tanks

H. Barthélémy, M. Weber, F. Barbier, Hydrogen storage: Recent improvements and industrial perspectives, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy 42 (11 (2017) 7254-7262

Classical type V tanks: thermoset based with classical ply thickness

- Prone to transverse cracking,
- Transverse cracking induces local delamination close to the tips of transverse cracks .
- Leakage criterion get compromised due to a percolating network of crack throughout the thickness.
- The percolated regime is not an acceptable regime, permeability criteria should be met on diffusion regime
 - Bring more structural stability?

Mikroni et al. "Design, Analysis and Testing of a Type V Composite Pressure Vessel for Hydrogen Storage". Polymers, Vol.16, 2024.

Our study: moving to thin-ply thermoplastics

Unidirectional Carbon-Fiber Prepreg(CF/PA6)

Fiber tensile modulus [GPa]	230	Material configuration	Sheet roll
Fiber areal weight [g/m ²]	40	Package configuration	Cardboard with 3" core
Resin areal weight [g/m ²]	23	Sheet length [m]	450
Vf [%]	53	Sheet width [mm]	250
RC [%]	36	Matrix resin Melting point [°C]	225
T _g [°C]	50	Thickness [μm]	42

Test items	Test Results	Test Method
0° tensile strength [MPa]	2300	JIS K 7165
0° tensile modulus [GPa]	120	JIS K 7165

Conde-Wolter et al. "Hydrogen permeability of thermoplastic composites and liner systems for future mobility applications", Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, (2023).

Our study: moving to thin-ply thermoplastics

3 advantages:

- 2 from “thin”,
- 1 from “thermoplastics”

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- 2 from “thin”,
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Advantage 1:

Thin plies eliminates transverse cracks

- Well-known Finite Fracture Mechanics result,
- Well-accepted observation in thermosets,
- Can be readily extended to thermoplastic laminates.

Nairn, Hashin, Parvizi, Hutchinson, Ladevèze and Lubineau [70s,80s,90s]

Our study: moving to thin-ply thermoplastics

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Fig. 4. The fundamental micro-meso link.

- Well-known Finite Fracture Mechanics result,
- Well-accepted observation in thermosets,
- Can be readily extended to thermoplastic laminates.

Fig. 5. Problem $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}|_{\Gamma_j}$: approximate solution of σ 's around an interface Γ_j .

Our direction: moving to thin-ply thermoplastics

3 advantages:

- 2 from “thin”,
- 1 from “thermoplastics”

Advantage 1:

Thin plies eliminates transverse cracks

- Well-known Finite Fracture Mechanics result,

- Well-accepted observation in thermosets,

- Can be readily extended to thermoplastic laminates, with additional dissipation sources.

Lee J, Soutis C. Measuring the notched compressive strength of composite laminates: specimen size effects. Compos Sci Technol 2008;68:2359–66.

Our direction: moving to thin-ply thermoplastics

3 advantages:

- 2 from “thin”,
- 1 from “thermoplastics”

Advantage 2:

Thin plies come with “better” microstructures

- Obtained by two spreading,
- Resulting in more “uniform” fiber distribution,
- Might be interesting for permeability.

Classical “Thick” Thermoplastics PP tapes

“layered-like” structures

“Bindle” structures

Thin 42 microns tapes

Our direction: moving to thin-ply thermoplastics

3 advantages:

- 2 from “thin”,
- 1 from “thermoplastics”

Advantage 2:

Thermoplastic bring more ductility, leveraging the classical “brittleness” of thin-plyies

- Thermoset thin-plyies are known to be very brittle,
- Moving to their thermoplastic counterpart brings the best of both worlds.

(a) $t_l = 42 \mu\text{m}$

F. Oz, A. Wagih, Y. Kara, M. Bahabri, G. Lubineau, Thin-shell thermoplastic composites with tunable out-of-plane properties: The interplay of layer thickness and cooling rate, Composites Part B: Engineering, 2025, Vol 299, 112381

Our direction: moving to thin-ply thermoplastics

Advantage 2:

Thermoplastic bring more ductility, leveraging the classical “brittleness” of thin-plies

Damage transition in GFPP with Matrix “C” (less ductile)

Damage transition in GFPP with Matrix “H” (more ductile)

Insights about Permeability of thin-ply based composites

Hydrogen feed

Permeability of thin-ply based composites

Point 1: testing with H₂ (not with helium) is key

- Many studies use Helium as a surrogate,
- This may result in totally different permeability/pressure trends.

Hydrogen

- Y. Sun, H. Lv, W. Zhou, C. Zhang, Research on hydrogen permeability of polyamide 6 as the liner material for type IV hydrogen storage tank, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy 45 (46) (2020) 24980-24990.
- H. Fujiwara, H. Ono, K. Onoue, S. Nishimura, High-pressure gaseous hydrogen permeation test method-property of polymeric materials for high-pressure hydrogen devices, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy 45 (53) (2020) 29082-29094.
- F. Oz, A. Wagih, J. Datta, B. Joarder, M. Eddaoudi, G. Lubineau, On hydrogen permeability of thin-ply thermoplastic composites, Proceedings of the 21st European Conference in Composite materials 8 (2024) 1163-1168.

Helium

- L/ Valentini, M. Bellachioma, L. Lozzi, S. Santucci, J. M. Kenny, Helium permeation through a-C: H films deposited on polymeric substrates, Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A: Vacuum, Surfaces, and Films 20 (50) (2002) 1647-1652.
- M. Flanagan, D. M. Grogan, J. Goggins, S. Appel, K. Doyle, S. B. Leen, C. M. Bradagaigh, Permeability of carbon fibre peek composites for cryogenic storage tanks of future space launchers, Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing 101 (2017) 173-184
- D. Schultheiß, permeation barrier for lightweight liquid hydrogen tanks, Universität Augsburg, PhD Dissertation (2007)

Permeability of thin-ply based composites

Point 1: testing with H₂ (not with helium) is key

- Permeability is decreasing with pressure,
- True for all tested sequences,
- Usually attributed to reduction of free volume under high pressure,
- Permeability at low-pressure is a safe design quantity if no additional damage

Permeability of thin-ply based composites

Point 2: thicker layers result in lower permeability (initially)

Laminate	Layer thickness (μm)
$[0/90]_{4s}$	42
$[0_2/90_2]_{2s}$	84
$[0_4/90_4]_s$	168

Permeability of thin-ply based composites

Point 2: thicker layers result in lower permeability (initially)

- All samples have been analyzed by DSC,
- Observation of a large proportion of γ phases, meaning that equilibrium was not fully reached,
- Clearly more crystallinity in thick samples.

Permeability of thin-ply based composites

Point 2: thicker layers result in lower permeability (initially)

- Permeability is decreasing quickly with crystallinity,
- From a strict “permeability” criterion, thicker layers are better in the pristine state due to high crystallinity

Permeability of thin-ply based composites

Point 3: think layers will however remain competitive at higher strains

Permeability of thin-ply based composites

Point 3: think layers will however remain competitive at higher strains

(b) [0/90]_{4s} at 1.25 % strain.

Limited cracking at higher strain with thin plies, as expected

Permeability of thin-ply based composites

Point 3: think layers will however remain competitive at higher strains

(f) [0₄/90₄]_s at 1.25 % strain.

Even based on thin-ply, thick layers are more prone to percolating damage.

Permeability of thin-ply based composites

Point 4: design of a 100 bars thin-ply tank

(a) P_i and Q as a function of t_w (pristine).

(b) P_i and Q as a function of t_w (compromised).

Permeability of thin-ply based composites

Point 4: design of a 100 bars thin-ply tank

(c) Required t_w for each criteria (pristine).

(d) Required t_w for each criteria (compromised).

Quick math about the total wall thickness:

Type IV: ~8 mm, Type V "Thick layers Th Pl": 7 mm, Type 5 "Thin layer Th": 5-6 mm

Conclusions

- Moving to type V tank requires to bring more stability to the inner layer (load-bearing liner) and to avoid permeation through the wall,
- Thin-ply thermoplastics are ideal to mitigate catastrophic cracking-induced leakage,
- Processing conditions and lay-up influence the crystallinity and by then the initial permeability,
- Thin-ply used as “thin-ply” reduce the permeability under loading train, showing potential for wall-reduction.

IsoSORP: Gravimetric Gas Sorption Analysis with Magnetic Suspension Balance

Magnetic Suspension Balance

- High-resolution mass determination under extreme conditions
 - At high pressures: < 700 bars
 - Temperature: -196 °C (77 K) – +1550 °C
 - In corrosive environments
 - Sample weight: < 25 g (10 μg balance resolution)
- Main application area:
 - Measuring gas sorption on porous particles for gas separation and storage
 - CO₂, H₂, CH₄

Experimental procedure

Laminate configurations

Processing

High-pressure environment

Characterization

Effect of H₂ pressure on microstructure

Fast-cooled laminates:

- High-pressure H₂ acts as an annealing agent:
 - Allowing amorphous phases to transform into crystallites
 - Formation of new unstable γ crystallites
 - Significant increase in crystallinity

Example 2

High performance Thermoplastic pipes for O&G

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Corrosion: Trillions lost

Burkle, D. P. (2017). *Understanding the formation of protective FeCO₃ onto carbon steel pipelines during CO₂ corrosion* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Leeds).

Energy environment is particularly aggressive to metal. (CO₂, H₂S, acids, ...)

Resulting in extensive and corrosion:

- Uniform corrosion,
- Pitting,
- Crevice corrosion,
- Galvanic corrosion / stress-assisted corrosion,
- Microbiologically Influenced corrosion...

To simplify, the key consequence is global or localized change in wall thickness

Classical metallic inspections target change in geometry

New materials, new challenges: just 2 examples

Joints in Thermosets

Bulk aging in thermoplastics

Size	Operational Temperature	Nominal Pressure (psi)	Outside Diameter (in)	Inside Diameter	Max Length Per Reel (ft)	Min Bend Radius (ft)	Reel Size (ft)	Max Reel Weight (lb)
4"	150 F/180 F	750	4.71	3.83	2,110	7.8	14.5	10,396
		1500	4.90	3.83	1,910	8.2	14.5	11,639
6"	150 F/180 F	750	6.87	5.60	870	11.4	14.5	9,550
		1500	7.20	5.60	460	12.0	16.3	9,295
8"	150 F/180 F	750	9.31	7.63	365	15.5	16.3	9,342

New materials, new challenges: just 2 examples

Bulk aging in thermoplastics

Thermoplastics may evolve in time

Chemical aging

- Thermo-oxidation (heat +Oxygen),
- Photo-oxidation (UV),
- Solvent/stress cracking (bleach, acids)

Physical aging

- Lower molecular weight (chain scission),
- Changes in crystallinity,
- Loss of ductility and mechanical strength

Time/temperature/stress/environment acceleration?

Resulting in bulk changes in:

Ductility, Mechanical strength, Permeability

Sensing technologies available for composite integrity

Many...but few really practical/operational for SHM

What is globally available on the market for composites NDT/SHM?

Far from being as mature as strategies for inspections of metallic infrastructures

Copyright: assetintegrityengineering.com

New materials, new challenges: the example of permeability

Hydrogen permeation tests of pristine samples conducted at 5-10-15 bars at 35 °C

Relation between crystallinity, structure and Permeability in CF/PA6

Hydrogen percolation paths of [0/90]_{4s} laminate after pre-applied tensile loading

Evolution of crystallinity: Pristine samples vs. samples exposed to 100 bars of hydrogen at 35 °C

Crystallinity versus time in CF/PA6 laminates Exposed to 100bars at 35°C

An example: In such material, tracking bulk crystallinity is extremely important

Types of energy

Mechanical Energy

Nuclear Energy

Chemical Energy

Electromagnetic Energy

Electric Energy

Thermal Energy

Types of energy

Mechanical Energy

Electromagnetic Energy

NDT&E techniques on the electromagnetic spectrum.

Yao Ren, Robert Skilton. A review of pipe cutting, welding, and NDE technologies for use in fusion devices. Fusion Energy and Design. Vol. 202, May 2024

New materials, new opportunities: leveraging non-metallic innovations

Smart materials

- Integrated sensors
- Printable sensors
- Multi-functional composites

AI generalized diagnosis

- Regularized data-driven technologies
- Direct data to fraud detection/Diagnosis

Sensor Printing

New materials, new opportunities

Smart materials

- Integrated sensors
- Printable sensors

AI generalized diagnosis

- Regularized data-driven technologies
- Direct data to fraud detection/Diagnosis

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Thank you!

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